

OLFACTOR HAS SOME CHARACTERISTICS OF METAPHOR

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Annotation. This article talks about the issues of olfaction and its expression, which is recognized as a new direction for linguistics. Speaking about olfaction, the author emphasizes that although this issue has been studied in world, Russian linguistics and Turkology, it remains open in Uzbek linguistics.

Keywords. Olfactory, smell, smell-based memory, cognitive-discursive properties of metaphor, olfactory metaphor, synesthetic perception, cognitive linguistics, pragmatics.

The olfactory metaphor is one of the current topics being researched by world linguists. In modern linguistics, all research on the study of olfactory metaphors is based on cognitive-discursive analysis. Today, the olfactory metaphor is widely used in the preparation of advertising texts. Because the importance of olfactory metaphor is high in the synesthetic perception of smell and in referring to images and ideas about real objects around. As a result of the synesthetic effect of perception images in the olfactory metaphor, conceptual directions of metaphorical models are distinguished. They are analyzed by the recipient from a cognitive, pragmatic point of view. The olfactory metaphor is superior to other linguistic tools in the verbal representation of odorous images. It is known that human perception of smells is a complex process of intellectual activity. According to research, people can smell about a trillion different smells. But everyone knows that not all these smells are called by their names. If we pay attention, most of the words describing emotional sensations in different languages belong to visual and auditory channels. The process of imagining and processing the information received under the influence of the sense of smell is also unique. According to Hugo Meyer, olfactory metaphor is such a complex linguistic phenomenon that it cannot be analyzed only within the narrow framework of one classification. [1:229]. Today, in the classification of olfactory metaphors, it is necessary to study their stylistic, structural-semantic, functional-pragmatic, nominative aspects separately. When studying the olfactory metaphor in the nominative aspect, it is necessary to use the cognitive theory of metaphor. Proponents of this point of view emphasize that metaphor is not only studied within the framework of linguistics, but human thinking itself is metaphorical in many ways [2:207]. It should be noted that elucidating the

cognitive-psychological and discursive features of metaphor is one of the problematic issues facing modern linguistics.

Olfactory metaphor is a phenomenon related to the process of perception of smells. Olfactronics (lat. "olfactorius" - fragrant) is a science that studies the possibilities of using smells in everyday life and industry. [3:56]

The term olfactory metaphor should be understood as a noun used to describe a smell. Concepts expressed through olfactory metaphors are polymodal. Perception of smell is manifested through the phenomenon of synesthesia, which is a complex psychophysiological process.

The intermodality of sensations can be seen through the phenomenon of synesthesia. The intermodality of senses means the perception of other senses through the influence of the sense of smell. A person experiences the impact of various smells in the external world. As a result of their perception, he expresses his understanding of smells through verbal means. This, in turn, shows the importance and relevance of the sense of smell in the cognitive process in linguistics.

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